

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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FOREIGN TRADE LIBERALIZATION AND ITS IMPACT ON A COUNTRY'S ECONOMIC GROWTH (IN THE CASE OF COUNTRIES)

Sirajiddinov Nishanbay

Doctor of Economics, professor of the Department of International Economics of the Faculty of International Economics and Management of University of World Economy and Diplomacy

Norkobilov Akobir

Doctoral student of Denau Institute of Entrepreneurship and Pedagogy

Abstract: This research paper conducts a comparative analysis on the impact of trade liberalization on a country's economy. The study utilized data collection from various countries and performed data analysis to investigate the relationship between trade freedom and economic performance. Additionally, the paper explores the role of government policies and institutional frameworks in promoting trade freedom and its subsequent impact on economic outcomes. By examining various case studies and policy interventions, the study uncovers the complex relationship between trade freedom and economic performance. The findings of this research provide valuable insights into the importance of trade freedom in driving economic growth and development.

Key words: trade freedom index, economic performance, GDP growth, trade policies, international trade.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu ilmiy maqola savdo liberallashtirishining mamlakat iqtisodiyotiga ta'sirini taqqosiy tahlil qiladi. Tadqiqot turli mamlakatlardan olingan ma'lumotlarni tahlil qilib, savdo erkinligi va iqtisodiy samaradorlik o'rtasidagi munosabatni o'rganadi. Shuningdek, ilmiy ish savdo erkinligini rivojlantirishda hukumat siyosati va institutsional tuzilmalarning rolini ham tahlil qiladi. Turli holatlar va siyosiy choralar misolida savdo erkinligi va iqtisodiy samaradorlik o'rtasidagi murakkab bog'liqlikni ochib beradi. Tadqiqot natijalari iqtisodiy o'sish va rivojlanishni ta'minlashda savdo erkinligining ahamiyati bo'yicha qimmatli tushunchalar beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: savdo erkinligi indeksi, iqtisodiy samaradorlik, YAIM o'sishi, savdo siyosati, xalqaro savdo.

Аннотация: Данная научная статья проводит сравнительный анализ влияния либерализации торговли на экономику страны. Исследование использует данные из различных стран и проводит их анализ для изучения взаимосвязи между свободой торговли и экономической эффективностью. Кроме того, в статье рассматривается роль государственной политики и институциональных рамок в содействии торговой свободе и её влиянии на экономические результаты. Анализируя различные примеры и политические меры, исследование раскрывает сложные факторы, влияющие на связь между свободой торговли и экономической эффективностью. Результаты исследования дают ценные выводы о значении торговой свободы для стимулирования экономического роста и развития.

Ключевые слова: индекс свободы торговли, экономическая эффективность, рост ВВП, торговая политика, международная торговля.

INTRODUCTION

Foreign trade liberalization has emerged as a pivotal driver of economic growth, particularly in the context of globalization. By reducing trade barriers such as tariffs, quotas, and subsidies, countries aim to foster a more open and competitive market environment. This process enables nations to capitalize on their comparative advantages, diversify their economies, and integrate more deeply into global value chains. The theoretical underpinnings of trade liberalization are rooted in classical and modern economic theories, which posit that greater openness to international trade enhances efficiency, spurs innovation, and accelerates capital accumulation.

In practice, however, the outcomes of trade liberalization are highly context-dependent and vary across countries. For some, it has led to significant economic growth, industrial diversification, and technological advancement. For others, it has exposed structural weaknesses, widened income inequality, and led to

deindustrialization in sectors unable to compete with foreign imports. These contrasting effects make it imperative to analyze the specific conditions under which trade liberalization contributes to sustainable economic growth.

This paper examines the relationship between foreign trade liberalization and economic growth, with a particular focus on the experiences of various countries. By analyzing case studies and empirical evidence, the study aims to identify the factors that determine the success or failure of trade liberalization policies. Special attention is given to the role of institutional frameworks, policy consistency, and global economic trends in shaping these outcomes. Through this analysis, the paper seeks to contribute to the ongoing debate on whether and how trade liberalization can serve as a catalyst for economic development in the modern era.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

Several studies have found a positive relationship between free trade and economic growth. There are many literatures on free trade and its impact on a country's economic performance that underscores the complex interplay of benefits and challenges associated with trade liberalization. Reyes-Heroles, Ricardo, Sharon Traiberman, and Eva Van Leemput, 2020 explored the effects of rising trade barriers on emerging markets in their study "Emerging Markets and the New Geography of Trade" [1]. The authors investigated how increasing trade barriers impact trade patterns and economic performance in emerging economies. Their research sheds light on the challenges and opportunities posed by changing trade dynamics in a globalized economy. Ribeiro, Joana, Adelaide Figueiredo, and Rosa Forte 2020 conducted a study on "Export Promotion Programs: Differences between Advanced and Emerging Economies" [2].

Their research compared the effectiveness of export promotion programs in advanced economies versus emerging economies, highlighting the unique challenges and strategies involved in promoting exports in different economic contexts. Aghion, Philippe, Antonin Bergeaud, Matthieu Lequien, and Marc J. Melitz, 2018 conducted a study on "The Heterogeneous Impact of Market Size on Innovation: Evidence from French Firm-Level Exports" [3]. Their research likely examines how market size influences innovation among firms exporting from France, highlighting the nuanced relationships between market characteristics and innovation outcomes. Bonadio, Barthelemy, Zhen Huo, Andrei A. Levchenko, and Nitya Pandalai-Nayar, 2023 explored "Globalization, Structural Change and International Comovement" [4].

Their research may analyze the interconnectedness of global markets, structural changes in the economy, and the comovement of international economic indicators, providing insights into the dynamics of globalization on economic performance. Semancikova, Jozefina, 2016 examined "Trade Openness, and Macroeconomic Performance" [5]. The research likely explores the relationship between trade openness and macroeconomic indicators, such as GDP growth, employment, and inflation, providing insights into the macroeconomic impacts of trade liberalization. Shu, Pian, and Claudia Steinwender, 2019 studied "The Impact of Trade Liberalization on Firm Productivity and Innovation" [6]. Their research investigates how trade liberalization affects the productivity and innovation capabilities of firms, offering valuable insights into the mechanisms through which trade policies influence firm-level performance. Singh, Ram, 2023 authored "Foreign Trade Policy 2023: Ifs, Buts and Nots," which discusses the intricacies of foreign trade policy considerations, uncertainties, and challenges faced by policymakers in crafting effective trade policies to drive economic growth and international trade cooperation [7].

Wang, Shaojian, Jieyu Wang, Xiangjie Chen, Chuanglin Fang, Klaus Hubacek, Xiaoping Li, Chunshan Zhou, Kuishuang Feng, and Zhu Liu, 2023 examined the "Impact of International Trade on the Carbon Intensity of Human Well-Being" [8]. Their research investigates the environmental implications of international trade on carbon intensity and human well-being, providing insights into the sustainability dimensions of global trade interactions. Lu, Marcus, 2022 emphasizes the historically proven benefits of trade as a driver of economic growth in his article "The Benefits of Free Trade" [9]. The author acknowledges a concerning trend of increasing protectionist policies worldwide, attributing this shift to a growing perception of trade as a competitive rather than cooperative endeavor. The ongoing China-U.S. trade war serves as a poignant example illustrating the repercussions of such trade conflicts on various sectors such as electronics and agriculture, specifically impacting commodities like soybeans [9]. McDaniel, Christine, 2022 "The Benefits of Free Trade and How to Get More of It" [10].

This policy spotlight article discusses the advantages of free trade and the challenges it faces in the United States. The author highlights that free trade allows for voluntary economic exchange across borders, benefiting both parties involved. The article addresses common concerns among Americans about free trade, such as supply chain issues, national security, and perceived negative impacts on economic growth, wages, and job loss [10]. Policymakers' tendencies to advocate for tariffs and trade barriers as a response to these fears are also examined in the article. Belay Seyoum, Juan M. Ramirez, 2019 "Economic freedom and trade flows" goes beyond the traditional focus on the macro determinants of trade flows and explores the link between economic

freedom and trade flows, and the roles of inward FDI and political stability in the context of this relationship. It also provides a novel methodological approach to examine this relationship [11].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research paper includes a combination of comparative analysis, data analysis, data research, data gathering, and econometric calculations, this methodology aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the impact of free trade on a country's economic performance.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Free trade, characterized by the unrestricted exchange of goods and services across international borders, remains a contentious topic in contemporary economic discourse. Proponents argue that it fosters economic growth, efficiency, and consumer welfare, while critics raise concerns about its potential adverse effects on domestic industries and income distribution. Understanding the nuanced impact of free trade on a country's economic performance requires a multifaceted analysis that considers both theoretical frameworks and empirical evidence. International trade policies play a crucial role in shaping a nation's economic performance (Reyes-Heroles, Traiberman, and Leemput 2020) [1].

They encompass a range of regulations, tariffs, and agreements that dictate the terms of trade between countries (Ribeiro, Figueiredo, and Forte 2020) [2]. Export promotion agencies provide valuable services to exporters, such as counseling and sponsoring participation in international trade missions and fairs (Ribeiro, Figueiredo, and Forte 2020) [2]. These services have been found to have a significant direct effect on export performance, as well as indirect effects through various pathways. Some countries, particularly advanced economies, offer a greater variety of export promotion programs compared to emerging economies. These advanced economies provided more financial support, informational services, facilitation activities, and education and training services, which contribute to their higher export performance.

Figure 1: The Advantages of Free Trade to a Country's Economy.

Additionally, international trade policies can also have an impact on nation's economic performance through the use of tariffs. One effect of tariffs is the well-documented welfare loss suffered by the domestic economy due to the distortional effects of tariffs. The imposition of tariffs can lead to higher prices for consumers, reduced market competition, and inefficiencies in resource allocation. On the other hand, tariffs can also be used as a strategic tool to protect domestic industries from unfair competition and to safeguard national security interests. However, excessive or retaliatory use of tariffs can lead to trade wars and further distortions in global trade. Another significant aspect of international trade policies is the impact of trade agreements. Bilateral and multilateral trade agreements can significantly influence a nation's economic performance by opening up access to new markets, reducing trade barriers, and promoting economic cooperation. However, the terms of

these agreements can also have implications for domestic industries, labor markets, and income distribution. It is important for nations to carefully consider the potential long-term effects of trade agreements on their overall economic well-being.

For our exploratory analysis, we conducted a regression analysis utilizing reliable data sources, where GDP per capita served as the dependent variable. The independent variables included capital investment, labor force participation, the innovation index, and the trade freedom index. All data in Table 1 utilized in this study was derived from the statistical reports for the year 2022.

Table-1: Statistical data from the year 2022 for regression analysis.

Country	GDP per capita, current U.S. dollars	Capital investment, billion USD	Labor force, million people	Innovations index (0-100)	Trade freedom index (0-100)
Austria	52084.68	129.74	4.76	50.2	79
Belarus	7888.26	15.93	4.99	27.5	76
Belgium	49926.82	157.93	5.37	46.9	79
Bosnia and Herzegovina	7568.8	6.73	1.38	28.5	69
Bulgaria	13974.45	21.12	3.15	39.5	79
Croatia	18570.4	18.84	1.73	35.6	79
Cyprus	32048.24	6.25	0.68	46.2	79
Czechia	27226.62	93.43	5.37	42.8	79
Denmark	67790.05	95.56	3.14	55.9	79
Estonia	28247.1	11.65	0.73	50.2	79
Finland	50871.93	75.4	2.85	56.9	79
France	40886.25	735.78	31.62	55	79
Germany	48717.99	1021.79	44.2	57.2	79
Greece	20867.27	46.01	4.65	34.5	79
Hungary	18390.19	60.14	4.98	39.8	79
Iceland	73466.78	6.97	0.23	49.5	81
Ireland	103983.29	126.44	2.67	48.5	79
Italy	34776.42	477.25	25.34	46.1	79
Latvia	21779.5	10.12	0.97	36.5	79
Lithuania	25064.81	19.11	1.49	37.4	79
Luxembourg	125006.02	14.49	0.34	49.8	79
Malta	34127.51	4.78	0.29	49.1	79
Moldova	5714.43	3.75	1.49	31.1	77
Montenegro	10093.44	1.89	0.28	30.3	79
Netherlands	57025.01	214.32	9.79	58	79
North Macedonia	6591.47	4.94	0.92	28.8	78
Norway	108729.19	128.8	2.98	48.8	85
Poland	18688	152.42	18.3	37.5	79
Portugal	24515.27	52.7	5.3	42.1	79
Romania	15786.8	80.88	8.3	34.1	79
Russia	15270.71	516.49	73.8	34.3	69
Serbia	9537.68	16.85	3.37	32.3	77

Slovakia	21256.81	26.64	2.81	34.3	79
Slovenia	28439.33	14.58	1.06	40.6	79
Spain	29674.54	304.56	23.69	44.6	84
Sweden	56424.29	168.18	5.72	61.6	79
Switzerland	93259.91	200.82	4.97	64.6	87
Turkey	10674.5	317.85	34.63	38.1	76
United Kingdom	46125.25	574.63	34.38	59.7	84
Armenia	7018.05	4.22	1.37	26.6	74
Azerbaijan	7762.07	9.46	5.43	21.4	67
Bangladesh	2688.31	147.46	73.86	19.7	64
Brunei	37152.48	4.31	0.23	22.1	85
Cambodia	1759.61	6.71	9.06	20.5	65
China	12720.22	7715.32	781.81	55.3	73
Georgia	6674.96	6.01	1.84	27.9	87
India	2410.89	1107.45	554.15	36.6	71
Indonesia	4788	392.37	138.1	27.9	79
Iran	4669.57	157.1	28.64	32.9	59
Israel	54930.94	141.48	4.45	50.2	79
Japan	34017.27	1131.68	69.11	53.6	75
Kazakhstan	11492.03	54.39	9.48	24.7	75
Kyrgyzstan	1655.07	4.32	3	21.1	73
Malaysia	11993.19	95.68	17.13	38.7	82
Mongolia	5045.5	7.26	1.39	28	74
Nepal	1336.55	15.5	8.74	17.6	58
Pakistan	1588.88	57.67	78.86	23	66
Qatar	87661.45	72.29	2.01	32.9	81
Saudi Arabia	30447.88	292.97	16.62	33.4	75
Singapore	82807.63	111.25	3.54	57.3	95
South Korea	32422.57	555.43	29.31	57.8	73
Sri Lanka	3354.38	21.21	8.77	24.2	47
Tajikistan	1054.19	3.8	2.61	18.8	70
Thailand	6909.96	137.93	40.91	34.9	72
Uzbekistan	2255.15	30.41	13.97	25.3	76
Vietnam	4163.51	133.63	55.69	34.3	79
Algeria	4342.64	78.61	13.02	16.7	57
Angola	3000.44	27.41	14.75	13.9	70
Benin	1302.85	6.36	4.8	14.6	61
Botswana	7738.88	5.44	1.15	23.9	77
Burkina Faso	830.04	3.33	8.33	15.3	61
Cameroon	1563.49	7.75	11.59	15.1	55
Egypt	4295.41	81.14	32.61	22.7	60

logarithmic transformations to each country's statistical data. Logarithms help linearize relationships between independent and dependent variables, addressing potential non-linearity and improving model accuracy. They also stabilize variance and normalize the distribution of residuals, which is essential for meeting the assumptions of linear regression. This transformation is particularly effective in managing skewed data, where logarithmic transformations can reduce the influence of outliers, leading to a more reliable estimation of coefficients. A model based on log-transformed data can be viewed as elasticities, providing valuable insights into percentage changes rather than absolute differences.

Table-2: Statistical Data from 2022 for Regression Analysis Using Natural Logarithmic Transformations of Economic Indicators.

Country	GDP per capita, current U.S. dollars	Capital investment, billion USD	Labor force, million people	Innovations index (0-100)	Trade freedom index (0-100)
Austria	10.86063	4.865532448	1.56025	3.916015027	4.3694479
Belarus	8.973131	2.768204124	1.60744	3.314186005	4.3307333
Belgium	10.81831	5.062151897	1.68083	3.848017675	4.3694479
Bosnia and Herzegovina	8.93179	1.906575144	0.32208	3.349904087	4.2341065
Bulgaria	9.544986	3.050220459	1.1474	3.676300672	4.3694479
Croatia	9.829324	2.935982269	0.54812	3.572345638	4.3694479
Cyprus	10.375	1.832581464	-0.38566	3.832979798	4.3694479
Czechia	10.21195	4.537212493	1.68083	3.756538103	4.3694479
Denmark	11.12417	4.559754322	1.14422	4.02356438	4.3694479
Estonia	10.24875	2.45530618	-0.31471	3.916015027	4.3694479
Finland	10.83707	4.322807275	1.04732	4.041295341	4.3694479
France	10.61855	6.600931161	3.45379	4.007333185	4.3694479
Germany	10.7938	6.92931127	3.78872	4.046553898	4.3694479
Greece	9.945937	3.828858764	1.53687	3.540959324	4.3694479
Hungary	9.819573	4.096675178	1.60543	3.683866912	4.3694479
Iceland	11.20459	1.941615225	-1.46968	3.90197267	4.3944492
Ireland	11.55199	4.839767887	0.98208	3.881563798	4.3694479
Italy	10.45669	6.168040463	3.23238	3.83081295	4.3694479
Latvia	9.988724	2.314513664	-0.03046	3.597312261	4.3694479
Lithuania	10.12922	2.950211758	0.39878	3.621670704	4.3694479
Luxembourg	11.73612	2.673458756	-1.07881	3.908014984	4.3694479
Malta	10.43786	1.564440547	-1.23787	3.893859035	4.3694479
Moldova	8.65075	1.32175584	0.39878	3.437207819	4.3438054
Montenegro	9.219641	0.636576829	-1.27297	3.411147713	4.3694479
Netherlands	10.95125	5.367470225	2.28136	4.060443011	4.3694479
North Macedonia	8.793532	1.597365331	-0.08338	3.360375387	4.3567088
Norway	11.59662	4.858260814	1.09192	3.887730313	4.4426513
Poland	9.835637	5.026639868	2.9069	3.624340933	4.3694479
Portugal	10.10705	3.964615456	1.66771	3.740047741	4.3694479
Romania	9.666929	4.392966575	2.11626	3.529297384	4.3694479
Russia	9.633692	6.247055927	4.30136	3.535145354	4.2341065
Serbia	9.163006	2.824350657	1.21491	3.47506723	4.3438054
Slovakia	9.964433	3.282413846	1.03318	3.535145354	4.3694479
Slovenia	10.25553	2.679650727	0.05827	3.703768067	4.3694479

Spain	10.29804	5.718868112	3.16505	3.797733859	4.4308168
Sweden	10.94066	5.125034834	1.74397	4.120661871	4.3694479
Switzerland	11.44315	5.302408984	1.60342	4.168214411	4.4659081
Turkey	9.275613	5.761579573	3.54472	3.640214282	4.3307333
United Kingdom	10.73912	6.353726355	3.53747	4.08933202	4.4308168
Armenia	8.856241	1.439835128	0.31481	3.280911216	4.3040651
Azerbaijan	8.957004	2.247072383	1.69194	3.063390922	4.2046926
Bangladesh	7.896668	4.993556953	4.30217	2.980618636	4.1588831
Brunei	10.52279	1.460937904	-1.46968	3.095577609	4.4426513
Cambodia	7.472847	1.903598951	2.20387	3.020424886	4.1743873
China	9.450948	8.950963242	6.66161	4.012772909	4.2904594
Georgia	8.806118	1.793424749	0.60977	3.328626689	4.4659081
India	7.787751	7.009815354	6.31744	3.60004824	4.2626799
Indonesia	8.473868	5.972205272	4.92798	3.328626689	4.3694479
Iran	8.448822	5.056882545	3.3548	3.493472658	4.0775374
Israel	10.91383	4.952158364	1.4929	3.916015027	4.3694479
Japan	10.43462	7.031458533	4.2357	3.981549068	4.3174881
Kazakhstan	9.349409	3.996180313	2.24918	3.206803244	4.3174881
Kyrgyzstan	7.411599	1.463255402	1.09861	3.04927304	4.2904594
Malaysia	9.392094	4.56100929	2.84083	3.6558396	4.4067192
Mongolia	8.526252	1.982379829	0.3293	3.33220451	4.3040651
Nepal	7.197847	2.740840024	2.16791	2.867898902	4.060443
Pakistan	7.370785	4.054737108	4.36767	3.135494216	4.1896547
Qatar	11.38124	4.280685807	0.69813	3.493472658	4.3944492
Saudi Arabia	10.32377	5.680070215	2.81061	3.5085559	4.3174881
Singapore	11.32428	4.711779921	1.26413	4.048300624	4.5538769
South Korea	10.38661	6.319742589	3.37793	4.056988776	4.2904594
Sri Lanka	8.118022	3.054472769	2.17134	3.186352633	3.8501476
Tajikistan	6.960528	1.335001067	0.95935	2.93385687	4.2484952
Thailand	8.840719	4.92674631	3.71137	3.552486829	4.2766661
Uzbekistan	7.720972	3.414771502	2.63691	3.230804396	4.3307333
Vietnam	8.334114	4.895074787	4.0198	3.535145354	4.3694479
Algeria	8.376238	4.364498918	2.56649	2.815408719	4.0430513
Angola	8.006514	3.31090791	2.69124	2.63188884	4.2484952
Benin	7.172309	1.850028377	1.56862	2.681021529	4.1108739
Botswana	8.954012	1.693779061	0.13976	3.173878459	4.3438054
Burkina Faso	6.721474	1.202972304	2.11986	2.727852828	4.1108739
Cameroon	7.354676	2.047692843	2.45014	2.714694744	4.0073332
Egypt	8.365302	4.396176058	3.48462	3.122364924	4.0943446
Ethiopia	6.934972	3.469790173	4.09017	2.791165108	4.1108739
Ghana	7.69783	2.444952334	2.67759	3.034952987	4.1431347
Guinea	7.323283	1.834180185	1.45161	2.451005098	4.1896547
Ivory Coast	7.818595	2.917230045	2.3618	2.879198457	4.3040651
Kenya	7.649359	3.078693794	3.20883	3.126760536	4.0253517
Madagascar	6.24725	1.150572028	2.73177	2.923161581	4.1743873
Mali	6.725394	1.264126727	2.07443	2.653241965	4.1588831

Mauritius	9.235641	0.970778917	-0.54473	3.538056564	4.4659081
Morocco	8.143805	3.680595235	2.4998	3.360375387	4.2341065
Mozambique	6.324896	1.960094784	2.68717	2.708050201	4.2626799
Namibia	8.523398	0.920282753	-0.03046	3.025291076	4.2626799
Niger	6.372295	1.519513205	2.28544	2.681021529	4.1431347
Rwanda	6.873402	1.232560261	1.62924	2.928523524	4.060443
Senegal	7.376965	2.532902848	1.63315	2.990719732	4.1896547
South Africa	8.819736	4.132442851	3.19335	3.394508394	4.2766661
Tanzania	7.084034	3.437850699	3.40453	2.965273066	4.0943446
Togo	6.848695	0.559615788	1.12168	2.714694744	4.1896547
Tunisia	8.228823	2.00148	1.47247	3.328626689	4.1896547
Uganda	6.871506	2.400618833	2.90362	2.753660712	4.060443
Zambia	7.284066	2.063058062	1.92132	2.76000994	4.2195077
Canada	10.92454	6.306713147	3.06152	3.927896355	4.4188406
Costa Rica	9.500422	2.537657215	0.93216	3.356897123	4.3174881
Dominican Republic	9.221404	3.631779862	1.64287	3.122364924	4.2341065
El Salvador	8.542338	2.004179057	1.0438	2.990719732	4.2341065
Guatemala	8.607621	2.761906874	1.95586	2.879198457	4.3174881
Honduras	8.019669	2.112634509	1.51732	2.850706502	4.2766661
Mexico	9.3498	5.805857599	4.07278	3.433987204	4.3438054
Panama	9.761787	3.451573589	0.71784	3.246490992	4.3438054
USA	11.24282	8.636468446	5.12509	4.123903364	4.3174881
Argentina	9.521539	4.711690029	3.06852	3.353406718	4.1108739
Brazil	9.09579	5.866666338	4.68905	3.481240089	4.0943446
Chile	9.639228	4.347823313	2.26488	3.526360525	4.3567088
Colombia	8.79848	4.222151267	3.24921	3.374168709	4.3307333
Ecuador	8.76269	3.257711849	2.17589	3.010620886	4.1108739
Paraguay	8.724705	2.452727751	1.22378	3.104586678	4.3438054
Peru	8.871481	4.002229273	2.90526	3.370738174	4.3944492
Uruguay	9.94247	2.585505848	0.55962	3.374168709	4.2484952
Australia	11.08368	5.989186955	2.64404	3.852273001	4.4998097
New Zealand	10.78764	4.152927886	1.08856	3.854393893	4.4998097

Table-3: Output of regression analysis statistics.

Multiple R	0.976818237
R-square	0.954173869
Normalized R-square	0.952460742
Standard error	0.309130885
Observations	112

Table-4: Output of regression analysis statistics.

	Coefficients	Standard error	t-statistics	P-Value
Y-intercept	3.79365841	1.421618494	2.668548858	0.008803638
Capital investment, billion USD	0.849285463	0.051156465	16.60172302	2.23903E-31
Labor force, million people	-0.884681203	0.047952931	-18.44894933	5.08194E-35
Innovations index (0-100)	0.601126374	0.15506766	3.876542505	0.00018311
Trade freedom index (0-100)	0.462210056	0.353217732	1.308569795	0.193483886

$$\text{Regression equation: } = Y = 0.85x_1 - 0.88x_2 + 0.60x_3 + 0.46x_4 + 3.79$$

The inverse relationship between GDP per capita (y) and the size of the workforce can be understood through the lens of economic principles, particularly when considering a controlled scenario where factors such as investment levels, innovation rates, and trade policies remain constant. In this context, an expansion of the labor force often results in a decline in the marginal productivity of labor. This occurs because, as more workers enter the labor market without a corresponding increase in capital or technological advancements, each additional worker contributes less to overall output. Consequently, this reduction in productivity translates into lower income per individual, leading to a decrease in GDP per capita. This phenomenon highlights the importance of maintaining a balanced approach to labor market growth, ensuring that workforce increases are matched by appropriate investment in capital and innovation to sustain economic productivity and improve per capita income levels. Understanding this relationship is crucial for policymakers aiming to foster sustainable economic growth.

Table 5: Analysis of variance.

	df	SS	MS	F	Significance of F
Regression	4	212.903546	53.2258864	556.9781	1.22E-70
Remainder	107	10.2251237	0.0955619		
Total	111	223.128669			

The results from the multiple regression analysis indicate a strong model fit, demonstrated by a Multiple R value of 0.9768 and an R-square of 0.9542, suggesting that approximately 95.42% of the variability in the dependent variable can be explained by the independent variables included in the model. The standard error of 0.3091 reflects a relatively low prediction error, contributing further to the model's reliability. Among the independent variables, capital investment demonstrates a significant positive relationship with the dependent variable, with a coefficient of 0.8493. This finding emphasizes the critical role that capital investment plays in driving growth. The analysis reveals that purposeful capital investment and innovation are crucial for enhancing economic performance, while uncontrolled growth of the labor force can be detrimental. Policymakers should focus on strategies that align labor force expansion with improvements in capital and innovation to foster sustainable economic growth.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

In conclusion, trade liberalization serves as a cornerstone in shaping the economic trajectory of nations, offering transformative potential when effectively implemented. By opening markets, reducing trade barriers, and fostering robust international collaboration, trade freedom enables countries to integrate into global value chains, attract foreign direct investment, and stimulate economic diversification. These outcomes often result in accelerated GDP growth, enhanced employment opportunities, and improved living standards for citizens.

Moreover, trade freedom fosters innovation, technological advancement, and the efficient allocation of resources by promoting healthy competition. This dynamic environment not only bolsters domestic industries but also enhances their competitiveness on the global stage. For developing nations, trade liberalization offers a pathway to industrialization and the opportunity to harness comparative advantages, while for advanced economies, it supports sustained economic expansion and market leadership.

However, the benefits of trade liberalization are not guaranteed and depend significantly on the accompanying institutional frameworks and policy environments. Well-structured trade policies, combined with investments in education, infrastructure, and technological capacity, are critical to mitigating potential downsides such as income inequality, sectoral dislocations, and over-reliance on volatile external markets.

As such, policymakers must prioritize the design and implementation of balanced trade strategies that promote inclusivity and sustainability. By addressing structural challenges and ensuring that trade liberalization aligns with national development goals, countries can fully harness the potential of trade freedom to drive long-term economic prosperity and resilience in an increasingly interconnected global economy.

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